

Low noise microwave generation with Er: fiber laser optical frequency dividers

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Abstract—We describe noise limitations associated with Er: fiber-based optical frequency dividers. A low-noise Er: fiber laser combined with optimized photodetection results in 5 GHz signals having phase noise floors of -176 dBc/Hz.

Keywords—microwave photonics; phase noise; ultrafast optics

Optical frequency division, where a stable optical frequency is coherently divided to the microwave domain by an optical frequency comb, has recently emerged as a technique to generate microwave signals with extremely high spectral purity. With this technique, 10 GHz signals have been produced that exhibit absolute phase noise below -100 dBc/Hz at 1 Hz offset, more than 40 dB below conventional room temperature microwave oscillators [1]. Such low noise microwaves have potential applications in radar, high-speed signal processing, and time and frequency dissemination.

Both Er: fiber laser and Ti: sapphire laser-based optical frequency dividers (OFDs) have demonstrated low close-to-carrier phase noise [2]. For offset frequencies greater than 1 kHz, however, Ti: sapphire OFDs significantly outperform fiber-based OFDs. This can be attributed to three main advantages of Ti: sapphire OFDs over Er: fiber OFDs; lower intrinsic noise, higher average power, and higher repetition rate. Here we discuss our recent progress to address these shortcomings in fiber-based OFDs to achieve: (1) the lowest fiber comb noise contribution to microwave phase noise, (2) the highest microwave power generated by photodetecting an ultrashort pulse train, and (3) the lowest phase noise floors from a photodetected Er: fiber OFD.

For a frequency comb to act as an OFD, the comb frequency spacing must be locked to the optical reference. This may be accomplished by detecting the carrier-envelope offset beat (f_{ceo}), as well as the beat between the optical reference and one tooth of the frequency comb (f_b), and locking them independently. In this case, the fiber laser OFD noise that dominates the microwave phase is residual noise of f_{ceo} , as shown in Fig. 1. Here, f_{ceo} is locked by controlling the fiber laser's pump power, and f_b is locked

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Fig. 1. Contribution of fiber laser OFD residual noise to the phase noise on a 10 GHz photodetected carrier for two different locking schemes. Noise is improved 30 dB at 10 kHz offset with single actuator lock.

by controlling the cavity length with an intracavity electro-optic crystal [2]. An alternative locking method is to mix in the rf domain f_{ceo} and f_b , and locking the resulting $f_{ceo} + f_b$ signal [3]. This keeps the comb spacing locked to the optical reference while f_{ceo} and f_b are allowed to vary. The OFD noise using this mixing technique is also shown in Fig. 1, where $f_{ceo} + f_b$ is locked by controlling the intracavity electro-optic crystal. At 10 kHz offset from a 10 GHz carrier, this is gives a 30 dB improvement over the independently locked f_{ceo} noise, and is to our knowledge the lowest residual noise of an Er: fiber OFD yet demonstrated.

For offset frequencies beyond 1 MHz, the microwave phase noise floor is dominated by photodetection limitations. In the detection of high power ultrashort optical pulses, space charge effects reduce the achievable microwave power, limiting the achievable signal-to-noise. This effect is exacerbated by the fact that the pulse repetition rate of fiber OFDs is often 10-100x lower than

Fig. 2. High saturation 10 GHz microwave power with an interleaved pulse train illuminating MUTC PDs.

the desired microwave signal frequency. Here we combine two techniques to generate the highest 10 GHz power yet achieved for ultrashort optical pulse detection. For improved power handling capability, we use a modified uni-travelling carrier photodetector (MUTC PD), built for high saturation current and high linearity [4]. The MUTC PD is flip-chip bonded onto an AlN substrate and contacted to a thermoelectric cooler for efficient heat removal. Such devices have demonstrated ~ 30 dBm of microwave power under sinusoidally-modulated illumination. In addition to the MUTC PD, a 5-stage fiberized pulse interleaver was used for large repetition rate multiplication of a 208 MHz pulse train [5]. Through the first four stages, the pulse repetition rate is doubled in each stage, resulting in a 3.33 GHz pulse train. The final stage does not double this repetition rate, but creates pairs of 100 ps delayed pulses. This gives an additional ~ 4 dB increase to the photodetector's 10 GHz saturation power, compared to the ~ 6 dB increase for each of the first four stages. Figure 2 shows the resulting 10 GHz microwave power for when the pulse train is passed through the interleaver, amplified with an Er-doped fiber amplifier, and detected with an MUTC PD. A 10 GHz power of +23 dBm with 60 mA of average photocurrent was achieved. This represents a ~ 25 dB increase in 10 GHz power compared to direct detection the 208 MHz pulse train.

For microwave power >20 dBm, the thermal noise-limited phase noise floor is < -197 dBc/Hz, and the shot noise contribution to the microwave phase noise is negligible due to noise correlations in the detection of ultrashort optical pulses [6]. Thus high power microwave generation creates the potential for extremely low phase noise floors. Since pulse interleaving and optical amplification were required to generate the high power of Fig. 2, investigation of any impacts they may have on the microwave phase noise floor is warranted.

First examined was the pulse interleaver. An analysis of shot noise indicates that timing errors and imbalances in the interleaver stages can corrupt the phase noise floor by degrading the degree of correlation [6]. To investigate this, a free-space pulse interleaver was used to carefully control the delay error. Phase noise on a 5 GHz carrier was measured by comparing against a Ti:sapphire OFD. The average photocurrent of the interleaved Er: fiber OFD signal was 4 mA, resulting in ~ 1 dBm of 5 GHz power. The Ti:sapphire OFD generated 13 mA of average photocurrent and ~ 9 dBm of 5 GHz power. As delay errors were introduced to the interleaver, the phase noise floor increased, as shown in Fig. 3. When no error was introduced, the phase noise approaches the thermal noise limit of the Er: fiber OFD signal at -176 dBc/Hz.

With the high saturation power available with MUTC PDs, optical amplification was needed to fully utilize the detector. Optical amplification inevitably adds noise,

Fig. 3. Phase noise floor of a 5 GHz carrier from an interleaved pulse train as timing delay errors are introduced into the pulse interleaver.

dominated by what is described semi-classically as spontaneous emission beating with the amplified pulse train [7]. It can be shown that this noise is analogous to shot noise, and is therefore expected to exhibit similar spectral correlations as discussed in ref [6]. As a test of the noise correlations of signal-spontaneous beat noise, the output of the free-space interleaver was then amplified with an Er-doped fiber amplifier, followed by illumination of the MUTC PD. The average photocurrent was kept at 4 mA. If correlations are indeed present in signal-spontaneous beat noise, delay errors should increase the noise floor, just as in the shot noise limited case. The results are shown in Fig. 4, where the impact of delay errors on the noise floor are evident.

In conclusion, we present record low residual noise, high microwave power, and low noise floor, making Er: fiber OFDs a viable alternative to Ti:sapphire OFDs for ultralow noise microwave generation.

Fig. 4. Phase noise floor of a 5 GHz carrier from an optically amplified, interleaved pulse train as timing delay errors are introduced into the pulse interleaver.

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